

The Human Resources Management for the Temple in Northeastern Thailand

Routsukol Sunalai

Abstract—This research purpose is to study and compare the administration of Buddhist monks at northeastern Thailand. The samples used in the study are the priest in the Northeast by simple random sampling for 190 sampling. The tools used in this study is questioner were created in the 40 question items. The statistics used for data analysis were percentage, average, and standard deviation. The research found that the human resources management for the Buddhist monks as a whole is moderate. But it was found that the highest average is the policy followed by the management information. The Buddhist monks aged less than 25 years old with the overall difference was not significant. The priests who are less than 10 years in the monk experience and the priest has long held in the position for 10 years are not different in the significant level.

Keywords—Buddhist monks, human resources management, Northeastern Thailand, hotel industry, the administration of Buddhist monks.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the globalization world ,the environmnet has been change very quickly. So when the organizations need to change for improve the organization performance to make it better. If not it will be very problematic. Clergy at all levels will need to changes such as adapting to the training of clergy folk. In particular, the obligations of public confidence and social knowledge management community. By the way have to be in the political, economic that related to the clergy, law and knowledge of the IT infrastructure.

Nowadays the world has changed with the emergence of new businesses in a variety of different forms on the inside and outside. The Buddhist circles have an impact on the prosperity and stability of the religion. The public priest must learn the tricks of social change. The priest must make a contribution to society, according to the Buddhist belief because the Buddhism in Thailand now is in the current situation that needs to be updated to reflect changes in society. But not for the life of virtue in Buddhism disappeared in the eyes of the general public [1].

Otherwise it will create "Crisis of faith or other parasites will involve for this issue [1]. These problems are the supervision of clergy. All priests are like still young and do not have more discipline. In the case of the relationship between the women due to lack of loneliness, lack of humility tarnished the image of Buddha will going down.

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Many administration temple are focused on developing the building more than development the Buddhist monks' interms of monk activities and Buddhist principles. Another problem is the management of religion is the about primate of Buddhist monks of each district. This makes no powerful enough to run all the causes defects in the operation easier. The members of the religion and the people lack a sense of owner religion.

Therefore, the development of the religious community are not mature relationship between the clergy and the people. The priest was not the social and religious issues. There is no sincerity in yours religion. This is a problem caused by the administration ministry. For example, the abbot of the temple had no craft, low levels of duty glitches, using the incorrect wisdom was not given the job. The current problem of clergy unfavorable to the development of the temple.

The clergy ruling have no unity of command in response to the force. The regulation does not act clergy to centralization it will lead to the Buddhist monk internal conflicting.

From the history and importance of the issue showed the Buddhist monks administration is an operator of the clergy. As though all the Buddhist monks administration are lacks understanding of management and lack the ability to adapt to the changes of the global era. This is the intention to study the state administration for the purpose of Buddhist monks in northeastern Thailand. That have adopted the theory of general administration to developing management to facilitate the administration of ecclesiastical. The results of this research will provide the guidelines that presented a preparation for training course as well. In additional will improve the management system of clergy in all areas that will be beneficial to them [2].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Buddhist Monks Administration

The ruling clergy has built up since the classic era. The main rule at all time is discipline that generate by the Lord Buddha. Nowadays the administration of the clergy and the religious and judgment. Together, the consortium made all attendees will provide the principle of discipline and will require consensus is important.

The discipline enacted for the purpose of organizing for all of the monks live together in society. To facilitate the development of spiritual life. So entrenched in the social disciplines pattern of conduct that is pretty good. Will make Buddha -Sacred longevity successor to this is because it is a symbol of disciplines. And representation of harmonies

decline or prosperity of Buddhism. So intimately bound and depending on the progress of monastic institutions is important.

The administration ruling clergy in Thailand today discipline is based on essentially continue from despite unremitting. The modified form of ecclesiastical governance several times. Both sides have separate denominational split whatever always support the ecclesiastical governance of the kingdom. The purpose of Thailand is the state religion and the sustainable of King Institution and sustained a permanent establishment of the sovereignty of Her Majesty.

B. The Present Buddhist Monks Administration

The present Buddhist monks' administration today considered regime the democratic together with the temple organization command line up to the temple abbot. As a rule, enforced commanded by the spirit of the Buddhist monks' administration of Thailand.

The governing ecclesiastical regulations requires the clergy has a primate divide and rule is the ecclesiastical center. The ruling clergy regional public organization of parents, clergy will be the council is acting governor and district administration to carry out the measure of regional or local.

The primate sector has the authority to rule on the hierarchy of the region as follow.

1. The implementation of the ruling clergy to adhere with the Buddhist discipline, Buddhist association rules, resolutions declaring apostolic commandment.
2. Control and promote religious education, advertise Buddhism to the public.
3. Control and Command abbot primate and novices who are in command or in their region and to clarify the duties of the recommendations in command to be completed.

C. The Present Buddhist Monks Administration Policy

The monks had been studying law and adherence to discipline and traditions cultural of the country. In order to sustain clergy initiates fair encyclical pontifical mission to observe the development of a stable, permanent to neat and classy of Buddhism.

The humanitarian and cooperate with public, private in order to measure the clergy and religion are well run and efficient. The study concluded that the Ministry of Buddhist Monks at the Temple in Northeastern of Thailand conduct the clearly policy and goals but it still has problems and the effects resulting from the administration of the clergy as follow [3].

The Buddhist Monks Administration

1. Policy Analysis
2. Management Finance
3. Human Resource Management
4. Information Management
5. Relationship with other organizations.

Executives must have the potential

The good executive must build a team to complete the task successfully. Management must respect to the members of

sincerity. Working and monitoring and come with the ability to plan and conduct meetings effectively and evaluation by the end. Ready to help team to communicate the work of the agency to the public understood.

The potential of this knowledge, administrators must also be moral such as honesty, responsibility, sincerity, gratitude is not selfish and greedy.

In additional the Buddhist monks' administration have to be motivating and propelling the high success is the ability to overcome obstacles and get ready to show the potential of knowledge and skills with the ability at the same time, striving to have emotional intelligence is known to be thoughtful. No monopoly on leadership at all times and on all issues, not the dominant group resolution for young people with a basic understanding between people with forgive, praise and honor others sincerely.

In summarize Buddhist monks at all levels it requires both art and science of management consists of the theologians in the management plan and organization, coordination, evaluation of the budget. The Buddhist monks must be managed proactively and to be fully effective and efficient in arts administration includes leadership and human relations in the workplace and come with the art of convince speaking as well [6].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Population and Sampling Design

Population are Buddhist monks in the Northeastern Temple province during the year 2012 from 377 districts and 55 person and Buddhist monks at a district for 322.

The size of the sample using the grid Krejcie and Morgan by using simple random sampling technic. The instrument used to collect the data was obtained from the literature review is questionnaire and bring the questionnaire for verification and correction by the advice of advisors and experts.

B. Data Analysis

Data Analysis from the survey of the status of the respondents will using frequencies and calculate the percentage, and interms of the administration of the Buddhist Monks of the district calculating the standard Deviation (SD) and the average (X) [4].

The research conceptual framework is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS

A. The Status of the Respondents

The result found the Buddhist monks period less than 25 years amounted for 50 percent, from 25 years up to a total of 26.3 percent for 140 people and 73.7 percent of Buddhist Monks period served less than 10 years for 72 percent, from 37.9 percent to 10 year for 118 people represent by 62.1 percent.

TABLE I
THE STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Information	Frequency	Percentage
1. Buddhist monks period		
Less than 25 years	50	26.3
More than 25 years	140	73.7
2. Buddhist Monks period served		
Less than 10 years	72	37.9
More than 10 years	118	62.1

The Buddhist monks' administration has performed at a moderate level ($X = 3.50$). Considering it was found that a high level in the third and two in the moderate side. When sorted by descending from the side that has the highest average is policy analysis ($X = 3.62$), followed by the field of human resource management ($X = 3.61$) and the lowest is management information ($X = 3.37$).

TABLE II
THE MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF THE MANAGEMENT BOARD OF THE SANGHA BUDDHIST MONKS DISTRICT LEVEL

The administrators and the clergy.	N=190		Meaning
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	
1. Policy Analysis	3.62	0.62	High
2. Management Finance	3.51	0.61	High
3. Human Resources Management	3.61	0.62	High
4. Management Information	3.37	0.65	Middle
5. Relations with other organizations.	3.44	0.60	Middle
Total	3.50	0.55	Middle

TABLE III
THE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE BUDDHIST MONKS ADMINISTRATION BY THE MONK PERIOD AND FINANCE MANAGEMENT.

The administrators and the clergy.	Less than 25 years N ₁ =50		More than 25 years N ₂ =140		t	P
	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	$\bar{x}$	S.D.		
	1. Policy Analysis	3.67	0.64	3.60		
2. Management Finance	3.52	0.59	3.50	0.62	0.17	0.87
3. Human Resources Management	3.61	0.61	3.61	0.62	-0.10	0.92
4. Management Information	3.36	0.61	3.37	0.67	-0.08	0.93
5. Relations with other organizations.	3.43	0.55	3.45	0.61	-0.21	0.84
Total	3.50	0.53	3.50	0.56	0.07	0.95

The different of Buddhist Monks period has no significant. It means that the Buddhist monk period less than 25 years and the buddhist monk period more than 25 years no significant in terms of policy, finance, human resource, IT for overall and in each aspect.

V. CONCLUSION

The result show the number of Buddhist monks are 190 people at the district level. If categorized by Buddhist monks timing period and position less than 25 years old is in the age of 50 year represent by 26.3 percent. Timing period more than 25 years a total of 140 people representing 73.7 percent of Buddhist monks. And the Buddhist monk's administration has long held the position for less than 10 years, with a total of 72 people represent by 37.9 percent. And the timing period more than 10 year are 118 people represent by 62.1 percent.

In the overall average of the Buddhist monk's administrators in the Northeastern province the majority is moderate but considering that the high level and three on the second level by the sort average descending. The highest average is the policy analysis, the second is the human resources management and the third is the information management [5].

In terms of policy analysis found that the administration of the Buddhist Monks the majority is at a high level. Such as

they found that the administration of the Buddhist monks has analyzed the goals and objectives of the policy of the set of guidelines and procedures in accordance with the authority. And their responsibilities clearly. The project plans to provide flexibility. Appropriate to achieve the desired goals, respectively, it is the average minimum is to analyze the impact of the policy practicality.

In terms of finance management, we found that the administration of the Buddhist Monks the majority is at a high level. It means that they are satisfied with the keep the money at the bank, also promote and support in financial practice for management plan for donations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author would like to thank Assoc. Prof. Dr. Luedech Girdwichai, the president of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand for financial support. Also, the author would like to thank to Asst. Prof. Dr. Prateep Wajeetongratana, the Dean of Faculty of Management Science for the full support in this research.

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